

**EXPLORING PARENTAL NARRATIVES TOWARD
SCHOOL SUPPORT, PARENTAL INVOLVEMENT,
AND ACADEMIC AND SOCIAL-EMOTIONAL
OUTCOMES FOR PUBLIC SCHOOL LEARNERS:
BASIS FOR SCHOOL IMPROVEMENT PLAN**

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Exploring Parental Narratives Toward School Support, Parental Involvement, and Academic and Social-Emotional Outcomes for Public School Learners: Basis for School Improvement Plan

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Abstract

This research examined parents' Personal Experience Narratives (PEN) and their role in supporting their children's learning process. Nine (9) parents were selected as participants in the spoken interview. The narratives conveyed in the oral interview were transcribed and examined using the Narrative Analysis: The Personal Experience Narrative Approach through purposive sampling. The components influencing the Personal Experience Narrative were analyzed using a route diagram, which depicted their relationships. Common among nine individuals were the challenges they faced in supporting their children at school. Furthermore, the narratives of the participants yielded six prevalent codes: (1) The Challenges in Parental Involvement, (2) Parental Perspective on School Support, (3) Technological Challenges, (4) Mental Health, (5) Parental Hopes on Strong Academic Outcomes and (6) Parental Worry on Socio-emotional Outcomes. Furthermore, the participants regarded strong support from the community members and fewer non-academic school activities to focus on the academic learning outcomes as priority areas in today's learning.

Keywords: *Parental Involvement, Academics, School Improvement Plan, Parental Narratives, Support*

INTRODUCTION

On an international scale, parental involvement in school has long been noted as an essential and positive variable in children's academic and socioemotional development (Lara & Saracostti, 2019). Family involvement has also been associated with positive school attachment on the part of children and positive school climates (Avnet et al., 2019), which is why education scholars have extensively studied how parental participation affects children's academic performance (Tan et al., 2020). Its impact on adolescent academic success has influenced parental engagement research because policymakers and scientists saw parental participation boost children's academic success. Barger et al. (2019) agreed that parental participation in children's schooling promotes social, emotional, and cognitive development. Differences in learning performance can be the products of family resources, such as financial support, academic guidance, family involvement, and language proficiency (Mishra, 2020).

Meanwhile, locally, the reintroduction of face-to-face education as a learning modality by the Department of Education (DepEd) in the Philippines follows various techniques (Fontanos et al., 2020; Gildo et al., 2023; Yambot et al., 2023). The decision was reached via a collaborative effort, including the World Health Organization (WHO) and other prominent

organizations, including the Department of Education (DepEd). Recently, a growing trend among students has been to use modular online or printed learning resources. It encompasses using self-directed learning resources such as modules, tangible or digital textbooks, supplementary materials, study notes, and other educational tools. The prevailing consensus is that modern society requires parents to participate actively in work and education. The study by Cariaga (2022) adds to the evidence that Dayagbil et al. (2021) presented that both instructional strategies and parental involvement improve children's academic performance. Parents' active facilitation of cognitive development is essential (Ma et al., 2022). Following reintegration into the school environment, children need support in reading, writing, and mathematics (Björklund et al., 2023; Hollands et al., 2022). Furthermore, Boonk et al. (2022) posited a hypothesis suggesting that many characteristics, including parental work, education, and the number of children, would harm the development of their offspring's flexibility abilities. According to Zhuang et al. (2023), parents must continuously monitor their teens' advancements in literacy, written expression, and numerical proficiency to ensure the academic success of their adolescent offspring. Duraku et al. (2023) and McGorry et al. (2022) underscored the need to deliver an education of superior quality and extend assistance to socioeconomically disadvantaged youth. Orbeta et al.'s research from 2021 found that

Filipino youth's mathematical aptitude is below the levels of regionally and internationally recognized standards. Mutaf-Yıldız et al. (2020) state that advanced home numeracy interactions are associated with children's mathematical skills.

Lara and Saracosti (2019) proposed that more research should be undertaken on parental involvement. Owing to the intricacy of educational tasks, Veas et al. (2019) proposed that individuals require environmental stimulation derived from both their behaviors and the conduct of others, as well as communication and social interactions. According to Pinquart and Ebeling (2020), parents must maintain positive expectations about their children's educational endeavors. Parents who actively participate in their child's education and cultivate high expectations are likelier to get favorable results than those who primarily monitor academic assignments and maintain connections with teachers (Gust et al., 2023; Orbeta & Paqueo, 2022).

Statement of the Problem:

This study aimed to comprehend the complex interrelationships between parental engagement and the socio-cognitive advancement of children enrolled in public educational institutions. The primary aim of this study was to include the viewpoints and recommendations of parents in a comprehensive approach to improving educational institutions and the knowledge of parenting and to deepen awareness of how several elements, including circumstances, perspectives, and personal values, influence parental involvement in and comprehension of educational support systems. There is a widespread belief that this research endeavor would yield significant findings and aid in identifying critical determinants influencing the expansion of public schools. More specifically, this focuses on the main research question below:

Research Question: "What are the parents' narratives on their roles regarding school support and parental involvement toward academic and socio-emotional outcomes for public school learners?"

Literature Review

The academic performance of students from affluent and underprivileged backgrounds is a significant issue, often due to variations in household income, educational support, maternal engagement, and linguistic abilities (Ibáñez et al., 2020; Mishra,

2020). According to Pascoe et al. (2020), students in secondary and postsecondary schools often encounter academic-induced stress, encompassing the burden of attaining exceptional results and apprehensions about acquiring subpar marks. Assistance from family and friends benefits one's psychological well-being and motivation, but obtaining financial resources does not alter these factors. Conversely, interaction models indicate that students from the second generation get more advantages from familial wealth than their peers from the first generation (Alinsunurin, 2021; Roksa & Kinsley, 2019).

The Republic of the Philippines, categorized as a developing country, has substantial obstacles in poverty and education. As a result, many people from economically disadvantaged households choose to cease their pursuit of education. Olivio (2021) reported on a research study in the Philippines that identified a notable correlation between parental engagement in academic activities and their children's academic performance throughout the first phases of formal schooling. The influence of parental involvement in academic affairs on teenagers' literacy and mathematical abilities remains a significant area of interest, mainly due to the limited local research on this topic.

Empirical research consistently establishes a positive correlation between parental involvement, metacognitive capacity, and academic performance (Ates, 2021; Bachman et al., 2021; Harrington et al., 2020; Metzger et al., 2020). Nevertheless, most of these investigations use experimental or quasi-experimental methodologies and focus on childhood education (Puccioni et al., 2020; Tan et al., 2019). The time of adolescence is of great significance in terms of its impact on cognitive and socio-emotional development (Newman et al., 2019). According to the metacognitive and affective model of self-regulated learning training, attaining academic achievement is contingent upon using metacognitive processes (Bernacki et al., 2023; Raković et al., 2022). Owing to the intricacy of educational tasks, Veas et al. (2019) propose that individuals require environmental stimulation derived from both their behaviors and the conduct of others, as well as communication and social interactions.

Self-regulated learning and family interaction predict academic success (Chang et al., 2023; Choe, 2020; Guo, 2022). However, most research on self-regulated learning has focused on schools rather than homes (Berger et al., 2021). Few studies have examined

parents' impact on middle schoolers' independent learning. Regarding children's subjective experiences with parental engagement in their education, learning regulation affects academic performance (Li et al., 2020; Otani, 2020; Xiong et al., 2021). Similar studies show links among family participation, educational administration, and academic success (Saada, 2021), and self-regulated learning influences parental involvement's effect on youth academic attainment (Luo & Gao, 2022).

Pinquart and Ebeling (2020) discovered that parents expect less from their kids. How children see themselves, how their parents act, and their involvement in school can all affect how well they do (Brandmiller et al., 2020). High hopes for a child's learning are significant (Szumski & Karwowski, 2019; Scales et al., 2020). Parents involved in their children's education and holding them to high standards are likelier to succeed than parents who only look over their child's work and talk to teachers (Gentrup et al., 2020; Passmore et al., 2020; Pinquart & Ebeling, 2020). Özdemir et al. (2023) undertook a study to investigate the relationship between learning-centered leadership, student academic achievement, and teacher participation, both within the professional community and in contact with families. The data obtained from a survey administered in 2019 underwent analysis with multilevel structural equation modeling techniques. The survey was sent to a demographically representative sample of educators and learners from 79 lower secondary schools in 12 distinct regions throughout Turkey. The results indicate that managers can improve children's academic performance by promoting effective collaboration and communication between educators and families. The notion suggests that directors' leadership styles impact family members' level of involvement and the engagement of non-Western educators in the professional community.

Nevertheless, several investigations have been conducted about this issue. Zhang et al. (2020) have noted that the current body of literature examining the association between parental involvement and children's academic achievement has produced inconclusive findings. Prior research has shown a range of associations between parental engagement and academic performance, including positive and negative correlations and instances when no significant link was seen (Papadakis et al., 2019). Exploring parents' narratives on school support experiences may reveal a complex tapestry of emotions, perceptions, and relationships (Newland et al., 2020; Zsolnai & Szabó,

2021). Since this study investigates people's lived experiences, concentrating on how they perceive and make sense of their surroundings, this study in the context of parents and school assistance might include comprehending their subjective interactions in several aspects (EscalanteMateos et al., 2020; Sprague & Ekenga, 2022). Parents may explain their expectations for school support and their children's educational goals. It may include aspirations for academic success, social growth, and emotional well-being (Amado & Jarque, 2022; Zhang et al., 2020). Exploring how parents view their connections with educators and the school system via communication and engagement might answer the question of how parents experience the methods of communication (Lara & Saracostti, 2019). Do they feel heard and appreciated while discussing their child's growth or difficulties? Recognizing the challenges parents encounter in obtaining or comprehending available help might include language obstacles, a lack of knowledge, or a sense of being excluded from decision-making processes. How school support impacts the connection between parents and their children might include sentiments of empowerment, dissatisfaction, or tension within the educational family dynamic.

Methodology

This research examined parents' Personal Experience Narratives (PEN) and their role in supporting their children's learning process. Nine (9) parents were selected as participants in the spoken interview. The narratives conveyed in the oral interview were transcribed and examined using the Narrative Analysis: The Personal Experience Narrative Approach through purposive sampling. The components influencing the Personal Experience Narrative were analyzed using a route diagram, which depicted their relationships. The researchers successfully validated and verified their results by the comprehensive and well-controlled collection and analysis of the necessary data. It facilitated the attainment of the most precise outcomes conceivable. A comprehensive literature review was conducted as a fundamental part of this technique to build a concrete body of knowledge, and objectives were achieved via the implementation of the procedure. Subsequently, an appropriate study design was created for the research question. Subsequently, the data underwent comprehensive analysis via qualitative techniques. As a result, it was possible to conduct a thorough investigation of the subject matter of the study. This technique yields insightful discoveries that contribute significantly to the existing corpus of

knowledge in the field and have practical implications. The survey included a varied spectrum of nine participants who had varying levels of prior exposure to school support, parental involvement, and academic and socioemotional outcomes of their children. The age range of the participants ranged from 38 to 45 years. Ethical considerations were duly addressed by using robust measures to protect the identities and ensure the confidentiality of the participants. Additionally, before the interview, informed consent was obtained from the authorities and all participants, thus upholding ethical standards. Furthermore, the interviews were conducted at the convenience of the one being interviewed to ensure the preservation of the participants' privacy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study analyzed parents' Personal Experience Narratives (PEN) and their role in supporting their children's learning process. Nine parents participated in a spoken interview, and their narratives were transcribed and analyzed using the Narrative Analysis: The Personal Experience Narrative Approach. The research identified six prevalent codes: Challenges in Parental Involvement, Parental Perspective on School Support, Technological Challenges, Mental Health, Parental Hopes on Strong Academic Outcomes, and Parental Worry on Socio-emotional Outcomes. Participants viewed strong community support and fewer non-academic school activities as priority areas for focusing on academic learning outcomes.

Parental Challenges at Home

Parents related that many responsibilities may result in difficulties managing one's time, emotional strain, reduced efficiency, and adverse impacts on family relationships. Juggling work obligations with children's school schedules, extracurricular activities, and family time led them to physical exhaustion and insufficient opportunities for relaxation. Their financial limitations increased their heightened worry and tension inside their home, exacerbating interpersonal difficulties.

Due to incompatible schedules, parents cannot attend Parent-Teacher meetings. They were balancing job responsibilities with their school commitments. Parents opened up that family time may provide a significant challenge in efficiently managing one's time for parents who belong to low-income households. It creates a psychological weight, which might mean the tension between one's work obligations and familial

responsibilities can lead to mental distress, guilt, and heightened stress levels. For example, sometimes parents get irritated or anxious when their students talk about expenses for projects with a very short deadline.

Due to work obligations, individuals may not have enough time to develop meaningful relationships with their children and establish strong emotional connections, resulting in emotions of shame and remorse. Parents were honest enough to say that financial constraints limited their ability to allocate time to activities supporting their family unit. While working longer hours or pursuing multiple careers can enhance financial stability, they experienced the lesser availability of time for family-related endeavors. They were worried that trying to manage several duties without sufficient support or time for self-care may result in heightened levels of burnout and stress, respectively. According to them, their well-being may be negatively impacted by stress and burnout resulting from the attempt to handle several responsibilities without enough support or time for personal self-care. The emotional strain and continuous altering of work and family obligations worried them because those things may bring adverse impacts on mental health and general welfare to their children, who saw their struggles, too. For their kids to prevent burnout and preserve their mental well-being, they advised them to prioritize self-care, seek assistance when needed, and include prayers.

Parental Challenges on School Support

Regarding school support, most parents knew they can participate in the different areas where the school can provide diverse services to help them successfully address their challenges. They thought schools are responsible for creating the necessary infrastructure to promote frequent and beneficial communication between themselves and teachers. They believed that it facilitated better communication between themselves and their teachers when they worked together. Communication with them as parents may include parent-teacher conferences, letters, text messages, or group chats that allow them to follow their child's academic progress and remain current on school affairs. The problem was that they needed all the luxury of budget to buy loads for connection or calls due to the high cost of commodities. Depending on the parents' backgrounds and experiences, this kind of communication may take various forms according to them. With their job commitments to sustain their support for their children in sending them to school,

parents were honest in saying that they need help when it comes to counseling their children. They expect that educational institutions have counselors who are likely available to provide guidance and support to their kids in some ways. Some parents mentioned their need to be supported in stress management methods, effective parenting tactics, and guidance on academic and behavioral issues. Even though they enjoyed participating in parent education programs offered by schools, which include workshops and seminars covering a variety of topics like parenting techniques, technology management, curriculum adjustments, and support for children's psychological well-being online, they still struggled to find time for their school commitments due to their jobs. With the rising commodity rates, they preferred to work than attend seminars and trainings in schools and online that included them. Sustaining their daily needs should become a challenge for them. To avoid this problem, they preferred to avoid attending meetings. If they are given monetary support, they believe they can participate in compensating their income for the day they miss at work.

Technological Challenges of Families

Children living in some families have obstacles when it comes to online learning and accessing educational materials owing to a lack of technology tools, such as laptops, tablets, and reliable internet connections. The unequal distribution of technical resources due to social inequality immediately leads to differences in schooling. Some parents may need more technological expertise to support their children using online learning platforms or educational software. Detecting technology challenges might hinder children's learning by obstructing the resolution of hardware or software issues.

Moreover, parents saw a significant difficulty in supervising and regulating the digital information children come across to ensure that it is suitable for their age and free from any possible damage. Parents believed it is necessary to maintain constant watchfulness and possess advanced technical knowledge to safeguard children from online hazards such as cyberbullying and disinformation. Parents had a headache supervising and controlling the amount of time youngsters spent using electronic devices, whether for educational or recreational reasons because they were only sometimes there for children when they worked. They knew this might hinder the practical support of children's education.

Worries on Learners' Mental Health

Parents found their students' sleep patterns changing as they grew older. They observed their kids to have suffered nocturnal wakefulness and sleep deprivation, which they believed may harm their academic performance and overall functioning. They knew as parents that adolescence has the least synchronized circadian cycle, and youths often suffer as they try to create their identity while dealing with disorientation. However, they were worried that their social environment might lead to poor sleep quality due to excessive use of social media and the internet. Since diagnosing their kids for their psychological wellbeing is challenging because a licensed psychologist is needed, parents used their authority to regulate smartphone and internet usage through scheduling and confiscating. However, this technique sometimes would not work when students said they needed phones for research and school. Parents were still trying to understand by monitoring their kids' sleep quality and habits and pre-sleep activities before they turned the lights off in their house.

Parental Hopes for Strong Academic Outcomes

Most parents observed the presence of public libraries in particular areas, and they expressed hope that their children could have these establishments locally where they can visit with actual books. Some parents know that several educational institutions offer libraries or resource centers to aid them in facilitating their children's at-home learning. Internet resources, literature, and instructional materials are accessible through these facilities. Parents were open to the idea of school collaboration with corporations, community organizations, and other educational institutions that can enhance the programming and resources offered by the latter. Using collaborative efforts, they agreed that these entities possess the capacity to augment training opportunities. Outside of the classroom, they believed they were responsible for augmenting children's education by enabling them to visit nearby libraries and other pertinent establishments.

Meanwhile, several families might find that educational institutions that grant them discretion in establishing attendance regulations or provide alternative modalities of instruction, such as online courses, are better suited to meet their needs. Consequently, parents achieved a harmonious equilibrium between their occupational obligations and providing care for their children and families. Parents get assistance in comprehending their

child's distinct requirements and delivering suitable care. It includes individualized education plans (IEPs), which strive to enhance the educational setting inside institutions. Institutions provide various services to assist families in managing their children's educational requirements with their personal and professional responsibilities. Extracurricular activities, or afterschool programs, allow students to extend their academic endeavors beyond regular school hours. These programs provide educational support, child supervision, and stimulating activities for kids while their parents are at work, enabling children to participate in secure activities and giving working parents more flexible schedules. However, parents preferred more academic work for their children than extracurricular to have better academic outcomes.

Parental Worry on Socio-emotional Outcomes

Parents believed that how they bring up their children significantly impacts the formation of their personalities, resulting in enduring consequences for their strengths, social and emotional adaptation, and mental welfare. They said they must understand the precise ramifications of raising children in the first phases of maturity. Meanwhile, parents exhibited variations in their approach to creating a home environment, but most participants preferred a nurturing and encouraging atmosphere defined by assistance and stability. They aimed to foster the cultivation of positive character traits and emotional fortitude in youngsters so that parents could be sure of their children's future success. Regarding parenting approaches, they prioritized the impact on a child's self-esteem and social aptitude. Occasionally, they had to assert authority, but they aimed to be more attentive and supportive toward their children. Parents recognized that enhancing their children's emotional well-being may impact their academic performance and socio-emotional outcomes. They advocated for genuine conversation and independent thinking, believing that it may enhance children's ability to solve issues and their sense of self-control.

Discussion

Work-life balance may fatigue parents and leave them too little time to rest. Money problems may also increase household tension and dread, harming relationships. Due to conflicting plans, parents regularly miss Parent-Teacher meetings. Mental anguish, guilt, and worry might result. Work may also make it impossible for parents to form strong emotional

attachments and vital relationships with their children, causing shame and guilt. Lack of money makes it impossible to arrange a family-helping time, causing concern and exhaustion. Parents advise prioritizing self-care, seeking assistance, and praying to prevent burnout and maintain mental health.

Parents have trouble accessing school services, including parent-teacher interviews, notes, text messages, and group conversations. Parents can only sometimes afford these services since items are so pricey. Since parents work to send their kids to school, they require help educating them. Educational institutions should have counselors to assist learners. School parent education sessions are popular, but parents work and need more time to make time for them. Some parents must work instead of attending training and seminars due to escalating costs. To avoid this, they may skip meetings. Because their families need more technology, kids may need help accessing online learning and school resources. Schoolwork is affected by social inequality since resources are not shared evenly. Parental computer skills may be needed to assist youngsters in utilizing online learning tools or instructional software. Parents struggle to monitor and regulate their children's internet material for safety and age appropriateness. Parents also struggle with mental health issues, including changing their sleep patterns as their children grow and staying up late. They fear their social life and internet and social media use will make sleeping hard.

Parents may assist their kids in succeeding in school by bringing them to public libraries and improving programs and tools with schools. They also favor schools with flexible attendance regulations and online learning options. Individualized education plans assist parents in understanding their child's requirements and provide the necessary care. Extracurricular activities, or after-school programs, let pupils study outside of school. These organizations provide academic help, child care, and entertaining activities for kids while parents work. However, parents expect their children to perform more schooling to succeed. Parents often worry about their kids' social and emotional outcomes because

they believe their upbringing affects their personalities, abilities, adaptability, and mental health. They emphasized how it impacts self-esteem and social skills and encourage honest discussion and independent thinking to help youngsters handle issues and manage themselves. Technology issues, mental health issues, and parental anxieties influence kids' lives. Handling these issues and providing the correct support may help kids succeed in school, socially and mentally.

CONCLUSION

Parental narratives yielded six prevalent codes: (1) The challenges in parental involvement, (2) Parental Perspective on School Support, (3) Technological Challenges, (4) Mental Health, (5) Parental Hopes for Strong Academic Outcomes, and (6) Parental Worry on Socio-emotional Outcomes. Work-life balance issues can lead to fatigue, financial stress, and family tension, affecting relationships and mental health. Parents may miss Parent-Teacher meetings, causing guilt and worry. Lack of money can hinder access to school services and help parents educate their children. Parents may also struggle with technology access, affecting schoolwork and resources. Mental health issues can arise from changing sleep patterns and staying up late and parents can help their children succeed in school by visiting public libraries, improving programs, and promoting flexible attendance regulations. Individualized education plans can help parents understand their child's needs and provide necessary care. Extracurricular activities can provide academic help, child care, and entertainment while parents work. Parents worry about their children's social and emotional outcomes, emphasizing how their upbringing affects their personalities, abilities, adaptability, and mental health. Addressing these issues and providing support can help children succeed in school, socially and mentally. Parents' time management issues create stress, decreased productivity, and family strife. Parents who care for themselves, seek treatment, and pray with their children may improve their mental health and well-being.

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